

POSSIBILITY OF IMPROVING STUDENTS' ENGAGEMENT AND ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN CHEMISTRY USING THREE-DIMENSIONAL PUZZLE-BASED INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY: A FIELD REPORT

By

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Abstract

The study investigated if three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy could improve senior secondary students' engagement and academic performance in chemistry. A sample of 143 Senior Secondary 2 Students from 4 senior secondary schools in Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria was used. The study adopted non-equivalent quasi-experimental research design. The instruments used for data collection were Chemistry Engagement Questionnaire (CEQ) and Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) with the reliability values of 0.89 and 0.93 using Cronbach Alpha and Kuder-Richardson respectively. Four research questions and four null hypotheses guided the study. The research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation scores while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Analysis of Covariance. The study revealed that there is significant difference in the mean engagement and academic performance scores between students taught Chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method in favour of three-dimensional puzzle-based strategy [$F(1,138) = 2204.094, p < 0.05$], [$F(1,138) = 102.075, p < 0.05$]. It is found that there is no significant difference in the mean engagement and academic performance scores between male and female students taught Chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based strategy [$F(1,67) = .402, P > 0.050$], [$F(1,67) = .172, P > 0.050$]. It was recommended that three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy should be adopted while teaching chemistry since it has been proved to be a viable option in enhancing students' engagement and academic performance for regardless of gender.

Keywords: Three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy, students' engagement, academic performance, chemistry.

Introduction

Chemistry which is a branch of pure science is introduced into the curriculum content of senior secondary schools because of its educational value, relevance to the need of the individual learner and society as a whole (Ajayi, 2019). Despite the fact that, the knowledge of chemistry to the society is very important, students' poor academic performance in chemistry as measured by their scores in senior secondary certificate examination appears to have persisted which is often blamed on poor teaching methods such as lecture and discussion methods. In the same vein, students' low behavioural, emotional and cognitive engagement in learning also appears to have persisted which is often blamed on poor teaching methods. By implication, poor method to

teaching invariably translates to students' poor academic performance and low level of classroom engagement. Based on this, the nation's quest for science and technological advancement will become a mirage, if effective modality is not put in place to incorporate innovative methods that promote meaningful learning and considering the importance of chemistry in all round development, there is need to ensure that chemistry is properly taught using innovative strategies in order to enhance students' engagement and academic performance. In the same vein, research reports advocate the use of self-learning strategies, as a way of enhancing students' problem solving abilities, active participation and learning outcome. Hence, the study investigated the possibility of improving students' engagement and academic performance in chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy.

Puzzles is a game or toy in which you have to fit separate pieces together or a problem or question which you have to answer by using skill of knowledge. Gardner (2013) opine that puzzles-solving is an active type of learning as it engages students with materials more than passive type of review does. Scott (2014) defines puzzles as problems that are fun to solve. Shapiro (2015) also refers to puzzles as problems or games that challenge ingenuity. Three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy is one of the effective innovations of teaching strategies that could enhance students' engagement, motivation, cognitive skills and learning outcome in science, especially difficult and abstract concepts. In this study, three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy refers to the use of three different forms of puzzles during chemistry instruction to test the ingenuity of the learners. In other words, it is the integration of three different forms of puzzles into chemistry instruction in order to enhance learners' engagement, creative thinking abilities, problem solving abilities and learning outcome. Though, there are various forms of puzzles, but the three dimensions or forms of puzzles emphases in this study are crossword puzzle, word search puzzle, and logic puzzle.

The choice of these three forms of puzzles (crossword, word search and logic puzzles) is because they are considered suitable for teaching chemistry concepts and also have the potential to promote the development of learners' scientific attitudes and science process skills. Crossword is a word puzzle that usually takes the form of a square or a rectangular grid of white and black shaded squares. The object of crossword puzzle is to fill the white squares with letters, forming words or phrases by solving clues, which lead to the answers. The answer words are placed in the grid from left to right and from top to bottom. Word search puzzle is a word game that consists of the letters of words placed in a grid, which usually has a rectangular or square shape. The object of word search puzzle is for learner to find and mark all the correct words hidden

inside the box in response to the questions that are asked by the facilitator. While, logic puzzle involves using deductive to correctly place numbers to a grid.

Students' engagement refers to the degree of attention, curiosity, interest, optimism and passion that students show when they are learning or being taught. Student engagement occurs when students make a psychological investment in learning. William (2014) has identified the three dimensions of student engagement as social engagement, academic engagement, and intellectual engagement. While all three dimensions are important, accountability can easily focus on the academic and the intellectual engagement aspects through a curriculum monitoring system that encourages and supports active learning. Hence, the study investigated the possibility of improving students' engagement in chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. What is the difference in the mean engagement scores between students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method?
2. What is the difference in the mean academic performance scores between students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method?
3. What is the difference in the mean engagement scores between male and female students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy?
4. What is the difference in the mean academic performance scores between male and female students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean engagement scores between students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores between students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean engagement scores between male and female students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy.

4. There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores between male and female students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy.

Research Design and Procedure

The study used pre-test, post-test non-equivalent quasi experimental design. The pre-test score constituted the covariant of the post-test scores. The study area was Makurdi Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the 1,734 Senior Secondary II students in the 23 government coeducational approved secondary schools. 143 students were purposively sampled from 4 schools. Two instruments known as Chemistry Engagement Questionnaire (CEQ) and Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) were used to collect data for this study. CEQ was developed by the researchers. CEQ contained two sections. Section “A” contained demographic information of the respondents, while section “B” contained a 20-item questionnaire which is intended to help students offering chemistry express their opinions on engagement in chemistry. Each of the items is a 4-point Likert-rating scale with 4 response options. CEQ is a researcher made instrument that contains two sections. Section A contains bio-data information of the respondents, while section B contains 40 multi choice objective items questions to which respondents are expected to provide the correct answer.

Cronbach Alpha was used to obtain the CEQ reliability, which yielded a coefficient value of 0.89. Kuder-Richardson (KR-21) was used to obtain the CPT reliability, which yielded a coefficient value of 0.93. Before the commencement of the actual treatment, the researcher used one week for the training of the chemistry teachers who served as research assistants. The training for the experimental group only differs from that of the control group by the use of three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy. The sample was divided into two groups namely; experimental and control group. CEQ and CPT were administered as pre-test by the researcher with the assistance of the sampled schools chemistry teachers which lasted for one week. Then, the actual teaching commences which lasted for four weeks. At the end of these periods, the pre-MQ and pre-CPT, were reshuffled and administered as post-tests which lasted for one week.

RESULTS

Research question one

What is the difference in the mean engagement scores between students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method? The answer to research question one is contained in Table 1.

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Table 1: Mean Engagement and Standard Deviation Scores of Students using Three-dimensional Puzzle-Based Instructional Strategy and Discussion method

Group	N	PRE-CEQ		POST-CEQ		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
3D puzzle-based	70	1.37	0.21	3.87	0.14	2.50
Discussion method	73	1.39	0.21	2.08	0.28	0.69
Mean difference		-0.02		1.79		1.81

The results in Table 1 reveal that, the pre-test mean scores for three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and discussion groups are 1.37 and 1.39 respectively with their standard deviation scores of 0.21 and 0.21 respectively. The post-test mean scores accordingly were 3.87 and 2.08 with their standard deviation scores of 0.14 and 0.28 respectively. The overall mean difference between the two groups was 1.81 in favour of three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy group. This implies that the students in three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy had higher engagement than the discussion group.

Research question two

What is the difference in the mean academic performance scores between students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method? The answer to research question two is contained in Table 2.

Table 2: Mean Academic Performance and Standard Deviation Scores of Students using Three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and Discussion method

Group	N	PRE-CPT		POST-CPT		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
3-Dimensional puzzle-based strategy	70	10.73	3.04	29.90	5.49	19.17
Discussion method	73	10.51	2.55	18.62	4.48	8.11
Mean difference		0.22		11.28		11.06

The results in Table 2 reveal that, the pre-test mean scores for three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and discussion groups are 10.73 and 10.51 respectively with their standard deviation scores of 3.04 and 2.55 respectively. The post-test mean scores accordingly were 29.90 and 18.62 with their standard deviation scores of 5.49 and 4.48 respectively. The overall mean difference between the two groups was 11.06 in favour of three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy group.

Research question three

What is the difference in the mean engagement scores between male and female students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy? The answer to research question three is contained in Table 3.

Table 3: Mean Engagement and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Students using Three-dimensional Puzzle-Based Instructional Strategy

Group	Gender	N	PRE- CEQ		POST- CEQ		Mean Gain within Gender
			\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
3D puzzle	Male	39	1.38	0.21	3.88	0.14	2.50
	Female	31	1.37	0.22	3.82	0.14	2.45
Mean diff. between Gender			0.01		0.06		0.05

Table 3 revealed that the male and female students had a mean gain of 2.50 and 2.45 respectively. The mean difference is 0.05. This difference, though small is in favour of the male students. This implies that male students had slightly higher engagement than their female counterparts taught using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy.

Research question four

What is the difference in the mean academic performance scores between male and female students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy? The answer to research question four is contained in Table 4.

Table 4: Mean Academic Performance and Standard Deviation Scores of Male and Female Students using Three-dimensional Puzzle-Based Instructional Strategy

Group	Gender	N	PRE- CPT		POST- CPT		Mean Gain within Gender
			\bar{x}	δ	\bar{x}	δ	
3D puzzle	Male	39	10.97	2.94	30.26	5.82	19.29
	Female	31	10.42	3.13	29.45	5.13	19.03
Mean diff. between Gender			0.55		0.81		0.26

Table 4 revealed that the male and female students had a mean gain of 19.29 and 19.03 respectively. The mean difference is 0.26. This difference, though small is in favour of the male students. This implies that male students gained slightly higher academic performance than their female counterparts taught using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy.

Hypothesis one

There is no significant difference in the mean engagement scores between students taught Chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method. The test to hypothesis one is presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Two-Way ANCOVA Result for Mean Engagement Scores of Students taught using Three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and Discussion method

Source	Type III sum of squares	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected model	113.561 ^a	4	28.390	560.722	.000	.942
Intercept	27.662	1	27.662	546.337	.000	.798
TPrCEQ	.002	1	.002	.037	.848	.000
Group	111.597	1	111.597	2204.094	.000	.941
Gender	.036	1	.036	.713	.400	.005
Group*Gender	.002	1	.002	.045	.832	.000
Error	6.987	138	.051			
Total	1371.268	143				
Corrected Total	120.548	142				

a. R Squared = .942 (Adjusted R Squared = .940)

Two-Way ANCOVA Test result in Table 5 reveals that there is a significant difference in the mean engagement scores between students taught Chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method in favour of three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy [$F(1,138) = 2204.094$, $p < 0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy is more effective than discussion method in improving students' engagement in chemistry.

Hypothesis two

There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores between students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method. The test to hypothesis two is presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Two-Way ANCOVA Result for Mean Academic Performance Scores of Students taught using Three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and Discussion method

Source	Type III sum of squares	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected model	4663.733 ^a	4	1165.933	26.774	.000	.437
Intercept	4136.918	1	4136.918	94.999	.000	.408
TPrCPT	85.421	1	85.421	1.962	.164	.014
Group	4445.054	1	4445.054	102.075	.000	.425
Gender	21.187	1	21.187	.487	.487	.004
Group*Gender	.573	1	.573	.013	.909	.000
Error	6009.470	138	43.547			
Total	94004.000	143				
Corrected Total	10673.203	142				

a. R Squared = .437 (Adjusted R Squared = .421)

Two-Way ANCOVA Test result in Table 6 reveals that there significant difference in the mean academic performance scores between students taught Chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy and those taught using discussion method in favour of three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy [$F(1,138) = 102.075, p < 0.05$]. The null hypothesis is therefore rejected. This implies that three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy is more effective than discussion method in improving students' academic performance in chemistry

Hypothesis three

There is no significant difference in the mean engagement scores between male and female students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy. The test to hypothesis three is presented in Table 7.

Table 7: ANCOVA Result for Mean Engagement Scores of Male and Female Students taught using Three-dimensional Puzzle-Based Instructional Strategy

Source	Type III sum of squares	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected model	.039 ^a	2	.019	1.058	.353	.031
Intercept	22.920	1	22.920	1243.463	.000	.949
TPrCEQ	.028	1	.028	1.546	.218	.023
Gender	.007	1	.007	.402	.528	.006
Error	1.235	67	.018			
Total	1048.187	70				
Corrected Total	1.274	69				

a. R squared = .031 (Adjusted R Squared= .002)

ANCOVA Test results in Table 7 reveal that there is no significant difference between the mean engagement scores of male and female students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy [$F(1,67) = .402, P > 0.050$]. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This implies that three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy improved both male and female students' engagement in chemistry.

Hypothesis four

There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores between male and female students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy. The test to hypothesis three is presented in Table 8.

Table 8: ANCOVA Result for Mean academic performance Scores of Male and Female Students taught using Three-dimensional Puzzle-Based Instructional Strategy

Source	Type III sum of squares	<i>df</i>	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected model	157.664 ^a	2	78.832	2.739	.072	.076
Intercept	3124.305	1	3124.305	108.537	.000	.618
TPrCPT	146.478	1	146.478	5.089	.027	.071
Gender	4.952	1	4.952	.172	.680	.003
Error	1928.636	67	28.786			
Total	64667.000	70				
Corrected Total	2086.300	69				

a. R squared = .076 (Adjusted R Squared= .048)

ANCOVA Test results in Table 8 reveal that there is no significant difference between the mean academic performance of male and female students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy [$F(1,67) = .172, P > 0.050$]. The null hypothesis is therefore not rejected. This implies that three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy improved both male and female students' academic performance in chemistry.

Discussion of findings

The study investigated if three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy could improve students' engagement and academic performance in chemistry. The findings of this study revealed that students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy had higher engagement than their counterparts taught using discussion method. This finding agrees with Agamber, Achor and Ajayi (2019); Ajayi (2019) who found that students had higher attitude, motivation and self-efficacy belief respectively when exposed to activity-related instructions than their counterparts that were exposed to conventional teaching methods.

The findings of this study revealed that students taught chemistry using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy had higher academic performance than their counterparts taught using discussion method. This finding agrees with Ajayi, Achor, and Agogo (2017); Ajayi and Ogbeba (2017) who found that students had higher achievement when exposed to activity-related instructions than their counterparts that were exposed to lecture and discussion methods. The likely explanation for this outcome may be connected to the fact that the nature of three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy such active engagement made it possible to improve the academic performance of learners taught with it when compared to the discussion method. The findings of this study also revealed that there is no statistical significant difference between male and female students' engagement and academic performance using three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy.

Conclusion

It is evident from the findings of this study that the use of three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy is more effective in facilitating and improving students' engagement and academic performance in chemistry than discussion method. By implication, this affirmed that students' engagement and academic performance in chemistry depend on the method of instruction. It is also evident from the findings of this study that no gender disparity exists in the performance of male and female chemistry students using of three-dimensional puzzle-based

Recommendations

1. Three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy should be adopted by chemistry teachers for teaching, since it has been proved to be a viable option in enhancing students' engagement and academic performance in chemistry.
2. Conferences, seminars, and workshops should be organised through Ministry of Education, schools administrators and professional bodies such as Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) to sensitize chemistry teachers with a view to improving their skills and experiences on the usage of three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy aimed at improving students' engagement and academic performance in chemistry.
3. Three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy is not gender sensitive; therefore, both male and female students should be exposed to three-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy to improve their engagement and academic performance in chemistry.

REFERENCES

- Agamber, S.T., Achor, E.E., & Ajayi, V.O. (2019). Enhancing students' motivation and self efficacy belief in solving biology related problems using frequent practical work. *Journal of the International Centre for Science, Humanities and Education Research*, 4(2), 20-30.
- Ajayi, V.O. (2019). *Effects of predict-explain-observe-explain and Vee heuristic strategies on students' achievement, metacognitive awareness and self-efficacy belief in Organic Chemistry in Ekiti State, Nigeria*. Unpublished PhD thesis, Benue State University, Makurdi.
- Ajayi, V.O., & Ogbeba, J. (2017). Effect of gender on senior secondary chemistry students' achievement in stoichiometry using hands-on activities. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 5(8), 839-842.
- Ajayi, V.O., Achor, E.E., & Agogo, P.O. (2017). Use of ethnochemistry teaching approach and achievement and retention of senior secondary students in standard mixture separation techniques. *Journal of the International Centre for Science, Humanities and Education Research*, 3(1), 21-30.
- Gardner, P.L. (2013). *Mathematics Puzzling*. Mineola Publisher.
- Nwagbo, S.Y. (2013). Effect of two-dimensional puzzle-based instructional strategy on students' attitude toward basic science and technology. *Journal of Science and technology*, 4(5), 51-62.
- Scott, K.M. (2014). Home puzzles in education. *Journal of Physical Science*, 23(3), 112-121.
- Shapiro, A. (2015). Science Teachers' Assessment of puzzle games in the teaching of environment concepts of integrated science. *Journal of Science Education*, 4(1), 15-22.
- William, K. (2014). Student engagement. Retrieved on 3rd December, 2019 from <http://www.chem/perform002/Usieni/pre/engagement.pdf>